

Sacrificial Polymers for Rapid Manufacturing of Vascular Materials

Mayank Garg, Adam C. Ladd, Evan M. Lloyd, Polette J. Centellas,
Mostafa Yourdkhani, Nancy R. Sottos

Outline

- Microvascular composites using sacrificial poly(lactic acid)
- Sacrificial polymers degradable at lower temperatures
- Rapid vascularization using frontal polymerization
- Conclusions

Static vs. dynamic materials

Fiber-reinforced composites

boeing.com

Biological composites

McKinley et al, *McGraw-Hill Higher Education*, 1st edition (2006)

Applications of synthetic vascular materials

Self-healing

Blaiszik et al, *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.*, **40** (2010)

Active cooling

Tan et al, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer*, **103** (2016)

Manufacturing vascular materials

Vaporization of Sacrificial Components (VaSC)

Sacrificial component

Esser-Kahn et al, *Adv. Mater.*, **23** (2011)

Pros and cons of sacrificial PLA

PLA with SnOx: 12 hours at 200 °C in vacuum oven

Pros

Availability, melt processability and mechanical integrity

1D Fibers

2D network

Cons

Matrix deformation/degradation

PMMA with PLA fiber

PVC with PLA fiber

Image Courtesy of Dr. Stephen Pety

Additional energy-intensive step

Goal: New sacrificial polymer that degrades at lower temperatures

Cyclic poly(phthalaldehyde) (cPPA) stability

Frontal polymerization (FP) of matrix

Frontal polymerization (FP) reaction

Robertson et al, *ACS Macro Lett.* **6** (2017)

Simultaneous FP and VaSC

DCPD $\xrightarrow{14.5 \text{ hours at } 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}}$
100 ppm Grubb's Catalyst
2 eq. inhibitor (TBP)

Free-standing gel
Courtesy of Dr. Ian Robertson

FP-VaSC

Wet spinning cPPA fibers

SEM cross-section of cPPA fibers

Solvent: Dichloromethane (DCM)

Solvent: Tetrahydrofuran (THF)

Coagulant:

Methanol

Methanol

cPPA fiber dyed with Nile red dye

Rapid vascularization during FP

Cross-section of microchannel

Summary

Conclusions

- VaSC using PLA is resource intensive and limited to high-temperature resistant matrices
- cPPA templates can enable VaSC at significantly lower temperatures than PLA
- Simultaneous polymerization and vascularization of thermoset matrices can be achieved rapidly using frontal polymerization (FP)

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